

IMPLEMENTING MULTI-CHANNEL DISTRIBUTION AS AN ALTERNATIVE FOR FISH MARKETING TO INCREASE FISHERMAN HOUSEHOLD INCOME IN SOUTH SULAWESI

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Abstract

This research aims to provide fishermen, as producers of marine fish commodities, and marketing institutions with an understanding of which marketing channels provide higher profit margins than others. Furthermore, this research also aims to increase producers' knowledge about product diversification to increase added value. With product diversification, producers will naturally expand their business partners, ultimately increasing sales volume and increasing business profits. This product diversification step demonstrates a shift in producer behavior from catch-and-sell (TLJ) to pick-and-sell (POL). This research found that the income received by marketing institutions involved in the fresh marine fish trade is influenced by the marketing functions they perform. The behavior of marketing institutions in each channel, where the selling price of fish reaches consumers, increased by an average of 17.50% to 30.67%. The increase in selling prices for each institution was due to the implementation of marketing functions, including transportation, packaging, cleaning, maintenance, preservation, and so on. The existence of alternative fish distribution channels as a marketing activity, from fishermen to end consumers, aims to achieve higher economic value. Collectors selling fish to retailers incur costs for several marketing functions, as do other marketing institutions, resulting in higher prices paid by end consumers. In conclusion, longer fish distribution channels tend to result in higher prices than shorter channels. However, it is important to note that the implementation of both long and short marketing channels is influenced by the characteristics of the product being marketed.

Keywords: Business Behavior, Distribution Channels, Fisherman's Income.

INTRODUCTION

National development aims to achieve several targets simultaneously: self-sufficiency in the fisheries sector, increased foreign exchange earnings, expanded employment opportunities, increased incomes for fishing communities, and the utilization and preservation of natural resources nationally.

Pangkep Regency was chosen because it is known as a dominant source of livelihood for its residents, particularly fishermen. The average annual production increase reaches 2.11%, or an average increase of 203,024.62 tons per year. The increasing fish production year after year certainly presents an opportunity for marketing institutions to act as intermediaries between producers and end consumers, hoping to gain services through marketing margins.

Production increase, as a concept, is not only seen as an increase in the quantity of physical products produced, but also encompasses all activities that add value to goods and services, including the marketing system, which is the lifeblood of a business mechanism (A. Harizt. 2001, p. 68). As experienced by producers (fishermen), production increases, but the sales value is often not significantly related to the level of income received.

The marketing system for marine fisheries products is highly complex, especially given the involvement of intermediary institutions (marketing agencies), each with different interests and methods. The methods and means of marketing fish from fishermen to end consumers naturally require significant expenditures.

The costs incurred by both producers (fishermen) and marketing agencies will impact the cost of goods sold and the selling price paid by consumers. According to Kenneth, Kenneth, (2011), the magnitude of marketing costs varies depending on the type of commodity, marketing location, the type and number of marketing agencies, and the effectiveness of the marketing efforts.

Marketing practices such as those described above directly harm fishermen/fishing households, the primary source of income for fresh fish businesses such as lamuru, layan, sibula, skipjack tuna, red snapper, rabbitfish, and others. The process of distributing fish from producers (fishermen) to end consumers requires various functional marketing activities aimed at streamlining the distribution of goods (fish) effectively and efficiently to meet consumer needs and desires.

The end consumers referred to here are local, regional, and inter-island entrepreneurs, considered the end users of goods. Marketing functions are carried out by marketing institutions related to or involved in the marketing process of a product (fish), forming a marketing chain, often referred to as a marketing system.

Pangkep Regency, the research location, is home to several marketing institutions involved in the fish trade mechanism: local retailers, Ponggawa (collecting traders, including cooperatives), sub-district intermediaries acting as agents, district wholesalers, inter-island wholesalers, and export wholesalers.

The marketing institutions involved in this commodity trade have two functions: as buyers and sellers, thus, in this pairing, a sales function occurs on one side and a buyer function on the other. The existence of these two marketing institutions illustrates the transfer of ownership or control rights by each institution over the fish commodity, thus increasing the utility of ownership.

The buying and selling mechanism for fresh fish caught at sea from producers to intermediaries (marketing institutions) involves three types of transaction behavior: (1) active-active type, namely each is active between the seller (producer) and the buyer, and usually this type occurs when fishermen have a production volume equal to demand, (2) active-passive type, namely producers actively offer their production results due to increased production results, but the buyer is less active, and usually this type occurs when the supply is greater than demand,

resulting in prices being determined more by the buyer including marketing institutions, (3) passive-active type, namely the opposite of the second type above, where the buyer is more active in making requests for goods (fish) and the seller (producer) is less active which may be due to reduced production results, and usually the prevailing price is more influenced by the producer.

The buying and selling function which is usually called the exchange function is very important to reduce obstacles to the transfer of ownership rights in an effort to provide satisfaction to consumers by considering effective and efficient marketing channels. With the transfer of ownership status Fish goods are traded through the exchange function.

The above activities serve to add value to the product's ownership. The end consumer will be willing to pay a certain amount of money for the product's value if the product is perceived and able to provide satisfaction commensurate with the cost, including service and product quality.

Fish trade, with market quality standards, is largely determined by the end consumer. Therefore, the role of marketing institutions is crucial. Marketing institutions carry out most of the marketing function due to their substantial capital. The costs incurred to meet consumer quality standards also influence the determination of the selling price.

In other words, the price paid by consumers is higher than if consumers bought directly from producers (fishermen). Marketing functions related to product quality include sorting/cleaning, storage, cooling, packaging, and transportation.

Other aspects include disciplined product processing to prevent waste and damage. According to Avonina, S. (2010), marketing costs vary depending on the type of commodity, marketing location, the type and number of marketing institutions, and the effectiveness of the marketing efforts.

The high cost of living that consumers must pay will reduce consumption levels and real income, and consumers will tend to consider alternatives by substituting spending for the goods they need. For example, when purchasing expensive fish, it is better to purchase affordable tofu/tempeh or eggs with high nutritional value.

Objectives

- 1) To understand the marketing system for fresh fish from the catch of fishermen at sea to the end consumer.
- 2) To understand the role of marketing institutions involved in the process of transferring fresh fish production from fishermen to the end consumer.
- 3) To determine marketing margins and the level of marketing efficiency of each marketing institution and its channels.

The benefit of this study is that it is expected to provide consideration for the government in making decisions regarding development in the fisheries and marine sector, particularly marine fish trade policies.

RESEARCH METHODS

1. Research Location

The research was conducted in two regencies, Pangkep Regency and Maros Regency, South Sulawesi Province. These locations were selected because they are the largest suppliers of marine and inland fisheries compared to other regions. Another reason is that the majority of the population depends on this sector for their livelihood, with an average of around 56.27% (source: Statistics Indonesia, South Sulawesi Province in Figures 2010). The selection of these two regions as research subjects is expected to inform the local government's considerations in the preparation of short- and medium-term development plans in the future.

2. Population and Sample

The population for this study was selected from several farmer-fisher groups in both regions with a minimum of 5-10 members. Based on statistical data from each of these two regions, 78 farmer-fisher groups have been recorded, meaning they have a membership population of approximately 624 people. If each member has a family of at least three, the total population living in this sector is 1,872.

3. Types and Sources of Data

The data obtained in this study include primary data sourced from empirical data collected directly from the research location through direct observation, interviews, and questionnaire distribution. Secondary data was obtained through a literature review of books, journals, and other necessary documents related to the research.

4. Data Collection Techniques

The data collection techniques used were several methods, namely interviews, questionnaire distribution, and literature study. The questionnaire distribution method was intended to determine and collect data on the volume of fresh fish production and the sales value received, as well as the profit level after deducting costs for the production factors used. Data obtained through interviews included the number of marketing institutions they partner with and the level of marketing efficiency in relation to the chosen marketing channels. Data obtained through literature studies, journals, and other sources provided relevant knowledge for the research.

5. Data Analysis

Based on the data obtained from the research results, the following analysis can be conducted:

1) Marketing Margin

To measure the marketing margin for each marketing agency, the channels through which the product reaches the end consumer are as follows:

$$M = B + \pi$$

M = Marketing margin

B = Marketing costs

Π = Profit

(Steven, 2011)

The total marketing margin can be determined by adding the margins of each marketing agency involved in the marketing of fresh fish:

$$M = Y1 + Y2 + Y3 + \dots + Yn$$

Where:

M = Total margin

Y1 = Marketing margin at market level 1

Y2 = Marketing margin at market level 2

Y3 = Marketing margin at market level 3

Yn = Marketing margin at market level n

To calculate the marketing agency's profit, the following formula is used:

$$\Pi = TR - TC$$

Where:

Π = Profit from each marketing agency involved.

TR = Total revenue (total receipts from each marketing agency). TC = Total costs incurred by the marketing agency.

2) Marketing Efficiency

To measure the level of marketing efficiency, the following formula is used:

Marketing costs

$$EP = \frac{\text{Marketing costs}}{\text{Value of products marketed}} \times 100\%$$

Value of products marketed

3) Analysis of Factors Influencing Marketing Margin

To determine the factors influencing marketing margin, a multiple regression analysis was conducted using the formula:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + E_i$$

Where:

Y = Marketing margin

X1 = Marketing costs

X2 = Marketing profit

b₀ = Estimated parameter

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Post-Marketing Treatment of Marine Fish

To ensure the quality and smooth marketing of fresh marine fish, a routine business for fishing communities in Pangkep Regency, marketing is a key factor influencing fishermen's income levels and requires special attention. To ensure that fishermen receive a fair price, post-marketing treatment plays a crucial role. In Pangkep Regency, the focus of research on the fresh marine fish trade, specifically the study of the behavior of marketing institutions that influence fishermen's income levels, reveals that post-marketing activities carried out by fishermen are limited to the initial stage, namely catching fish at sea, preserving it, transporting it, and selling it fresh. Meanwhile, the sorting, cleaning, preserving, packing, and transporting stages are generally handled by marketing institutions.

To implement efficient post-marketing, fishermen must shift their marketing model from a single channel to a multi-channel one. The findings of this study indicate the existence of a mono-channel marketing system, where some fishermen have regular customers with intermediary traders, commonly known as ponggawa. This institution initially provides capital/loans to fishermen in need, with a business contract that requires the fishermen to sell their catch to the intermediary trader. This type of business contract model, where prices are generally determined by the trader and tends to be less profitable for the fishermen. For a clearer picture of the post-marketing treatment of fresh sea fish, see the following chart:

Figure 1 Post-Marketing Treatment of Fresh Sea Fish

Post-marketing activities are generally carried out by marketing institutions, including retailers, collectors, wholesalers, agents, and inter-island traders, with most of the work performed by their own labor.

Meanwhile, fishermen, as producers of fresh fish, prefer to sell their catch directly to intermediaries or marketing institutions, performing fewer marketing functions. This is because fishermen face several limitations, such as time and cost, for the marketing process. Consequently, the price paid to intermediaries is insignificant in relation to their income.

Marketing, in principle, is the flow of goods from producers to consumers. This flow of goods is made possible by the role of marketing institutions, whose role is highly dependent on the prevailing market system and the characteristics of the flow of goods being marketed. Therefore, this concept is often referred to as a marketing channel, which plays a crucial role, particularly in determining price levels within each marketing institution.

Table 1: Marketing function activities carried out at various levels of behavior of fresh sea fish marketing institutions

No.	Behavior	Activity
01	Fisherman	- Fishing
		- Storage
		- Preservation
		- Transportation
		- Sale
02	Collector traders	- Purchase
		- Cleaning
		- Preservation
		- Transportation
		- Sale
03	Wholesalers at TPI	- Purchase
		- Sorting
		- Preservation
		- Packing
		- Transportation
04	Retail traders	- Sale
		- Purchase
		- Sort
		- Preservation
		- Sale

Table 1. above shows that post-marketing activities, including the implementation of marketing functions, are generally carried out by marketing institutions, resulting in increased costs, thus affecting the total cost per unit of product/fish.

This description demonstrates that marketing institutions play a crucial role in the fresh seafood trade, which benefits all parties, including increasing regional income and employment.

2. Marine Fish Marketing Channels

In Pangkep Regency, several marketing institutions participate in the marketing of marine fish, particularly fresh fish (fresh fish from the sea) and freshwater fish (farmed fish). Several intermediary traders/marketing institutions are involved in the marketing process, including: (1) collectors/pongawa (collectors), (2) commission agents, (3) wholesalers, (4) retailers/pagandeng (manufacturers), and (5) end consumers.

Fishermen, as producers of fresh seafood (fresh fish), generally fish at sea day and night, catching, preserving, transporting, and then selling the fish to marketing institutions / intermediary traders in basket quantities.

To be more precise, the marketing channel for this freshwater fish (sea fish) in Pangkep Regency serves as a place for marketing institutions and end consumers. Business costs and revenues.

Sea fish commodities in the fisheries and marine sector are the primary livelihood for the majority of Pangkep Regency's population, where this area is known as one of the regions with many fishing islands, hence the name Pangkep Islands. The marketing channels through which sea fish trade in Pangkep Regency operates are as follows:

Figure 2: Marine Fish Marketing Channels

Channel I

Analysis of costs, margins, and profits for this channel can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of costs, margins, and revenue for collector-level traders (Rp/kg)

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru	Kakap	Layan	Sibula	Cakalang	Baronan
01.	Purchase	22.500	17.500	9.100	2.250	15.000	27.000
02.	Marketing costs:						
	• Transport	2.500	1.750	910	225	1.500	1.350
	• Cleaning	1.500	1.225	637	157,70	1.050	-
	• Sorting	1.350	875	364	90,00	600	-
	• Preservation	1.125	700	-	-	450	2.160
	• Packing	2.250	525	-	-	300	810
	• Storage	-	350	-	-	-	-
03.	Total cost	8.725	5.425	1.911	332	3.900	4.320
04.	Cost of goods sold	31.225	22.925	11.011	2.582	18.900	31.320
05.	Selling price	37.470	28.656	14.314	3.099	22.680	40.716
06.	Income	6.245	5.731	3.303	516	3.780	9.396
07.	Marketing margin	14.970	11.156	5.214	849	7.680	13.716
08.	Mark-up	20,540	25,190	30,320	17,50	28,88	30,67

Source: Primary data after processing

Table 2 above illustrates the income received by middlemen/collectors. Marketing functions are not performed on some fish species, but this does not affect income levels, but tends to increase, such as for baronan and lamuru fish. The behavior of marketing/collector institutions in this channel has set selling prices higher by between 17.50% and 30.67%. Furthermore, an analysis of costs, margins, and revenues for sub-district wholesalers can be seen in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Analysis of Costs, Margins, and Revenues at the Sub-district Wholesaler Level (Rp/Kg)

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru	Kakap	Layan	Sibula	Cakalang	Baronan
01.	Purchase	37.470	28.656	14.314	3.099	22.680	40.716
02.	Marketing costs:						
	• Transport	2.500	1.750	910	225	1.500	1.350
	• Cleaning	-	-	668	164	-	-
	• Sorting	1.417	918	382	94	-	-
	• Preservation	1.181	735	715	154	1.134	2.203
	• Packing	2.362	551	750	161	315	850
	• Storage	374	357	286	61	453	814
03.	Total cost	7.834	4.311	3.711	859	3.402	8.217
04.	Cost of goods sold	45.304	32.967	18.025	3.958	26.082	48.933
05.	Selling price	49.834	36.263	19.828	4.354	28.690	53.826
06.	Income	4.530	3.296	1.803	396	2.607	4.893
07.	Marketing margin	12.364	7.607	5.514	1.255	6.010	13.110
08.	Mark-up	10,00	12,32	10,02	10,05	9,20	15,59

Source: Primary data after processing

Table 3 above shows several treatments for fish types processed by sub-district wholesalers, which are related to marketing functions such as sorting and packaging. These marketing institutions significantly impact revenue levels. Furthermore, these wholesalers mark up sales to district/city wholesalers between 10% and 15.59%.

Compared to the marketing functions carried out by collectors and sub-district wholesalers, collectors perform more of these functions, resulting in a difference in the percentage of selling price increases, with collectors receiving a higher percentage.

Furthermore, an analysis of costs, margins, and revenue levels for district/city wholesalers can be seen in Table 4 below:

Table 4: Analysis of Costs, Margins, and Revenue for District Wholesalers (Rp/Kg)

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru	Kakap	Layan	Sibula	Cakalang	Baronan
01.	Purchase	49.834	36.263	19.828	4.354	28.690	53.826
02.	Marketing costs:						
	• Transport	2.750	1.925	910	1.001	1.650	1.485
	• Cleaning	2.493	1.813	701	172	1.435	2.691
	• Sorting	1.417	918	382	94	-	-
	• Preservation	1.445	963	401	99	574	1.076
	• Packing	997	725	715	396	573	538
	• Storage	382	363	292	63	462	830
03.	Total cost	8.565	6.346	3.133	1.894	5.012	7.479
04.	Cost of goods sold	58.399	42.609	22.961	6.248	33.702	61.305
05.	Selling price	63.655	46.870	25.716	6.873	38.757	72.033
06.	Income	5.256	4.261	2.755	625	5.055	10.728
07.	Marketing margin	13.821	10.607	6.888	2.519	10.067	18.207
08.	Mark-up	9,19	11,19	15,00	10,00	10,00	12,00

Source: Primary data after processing

Table 4 above describes marketing activities for sub-district wholesalers, namely after purchasing fresh sea fish from collectors, then carrying out several marketing functions by spending a total cost on each type of fish with different amounts.

The difference in total costs incurred directly affects the level of income and margin received by sub-district wholesalers, but the mark-up level is between 9.19% to 15%. Paying attention to the results of the analysis of expenses and income obtained by this marketing institution is not too far from the collector traders.

Based on the results of interviews with the head of the marine fish trader group in Labbakang Regency, Dg. Jamal said that the price increase applied to consumers, both in industry, retailers and household consumers is not too high with an average of 12%.

Furthermore, the analysis of costs, margins and income at the retail level traders can be seen in Table 5 below:

Table 5: Analysis of Costs, Margins and Revenues at the Retailer Level

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru	Kakap	Layan	Sibula	Cakalang	Baronan
01.	Purchase	63.655	46.870	25.716	6.873	38.757	72.033
02.	Marketing costs:						
	• Transport	638	469	257	69	387	720
	• Cleaning	-	-	-	-	-	-
	• Sorting	-	-	-	-	-	-
	• Preservation	1.007	732	722	400	543	578
	• Packing	-	-	-	-	-	-
	• Storage	1.200	1.200	1.200	1.200	1.200	1.200
03.	Total cost	2.845	2.401	2.179	1.669	2.130	2.498
04.	Cost of goods sold	66.500	49.271	27.895	8.542	40.887	74.531
05.	Selling price	73.150	54.198	33.474	8.969	44.976	81.984
06.	Income	6.650	4.927	5.579	427	4.089	7.453
07.	Marketing margin	9.495	7.328	7.758	2.096	6.219	9.951
08.	Mark-up	10,00	10,00	15,00	9,00	10,00	10,00

Source: Primary data after processing

After processing the data from the marketing activities carried out by retailers, the analysis results show that the marketing institution (retailer) carries out three marketing activities: transportation of goods, preservation, and levies, all of which incur costs as outlined in Table 5.

Furthermore, the expenses paid to these three marketing functions reduce the retailer's income. Therefore, it can be concluded that the more marketing functions performed by the marketing institution, the higher the cost of the marketing process, resulting in a decrease in the retailer's income/profit.

Channel II

In the marine fish marketing structure, it appears that producers and marketing institutions have distance and time constraints on the way to the final consumer, including the costs incurred by each marketing institution to deliver the product/fish marketed through the channels used.

This second channel involves two marketing institutions: collectors and distributors. For greater clarity, the following quantitative breakdown of the total costs, margins, and revenue

levels for each institution is presented in Table 6:

Table 6: Analysis of Costs, Margins, and Revenue from Collector to Retailer Level (Rp/Kg)

No.	Description	Types of Fish					
		Lamuru	Kakap	Layan	Sibula	Cakalang	Baronan
01.	Purchase	22.500	17.500	9.100	2.250	15.000	27.000
02.	Marketing costs:						
	• Transport	2.500	1.750	910	225	1.500	1.350
	• Cleaning	1.500	1.225	637	157,70	1.050	-
	• Sorting	1.350	875	364	90,00	600	-
	• Preservation	1.125	700	-	-	450	2.160
	• Packing	2.250	525	-	-	300	810
	• Storage	-	350	-	-	-	-
01.	Total cost	8.725	5.425	1.911	332	3.900	4.320
02.	Cost of goods sold	31.225	22.925	11.011	2.582	18.900	31.320
03.	Selling price	40.593	29.802	18.186	2.840	20.790	34.452
03.	Income	9.368	6.877	7.175	258	1.890	3.132
04.	Marketing margin	18.093	12.302	9.086	590	5.790	7.452
05.	Mark-up	30,00	30,00	15,25	10,17	28,88	30,67

Table 6 above illustrates that the income earned by wholesalers is higher than through the primary channel. This occurs because this channel is shorter and the selling price is higher due to the smaller purchase volume of retailers compared to the purchase volume of sub-district wholesalers.

Meanwhile, the cost price and selling price are marked up between 10.17% and 30.67%, with varying profit levels based on the marketing functions performed by each marketing agency.

3. Margin and Income

Marketing fresh marine fish produced by fishermen through several marketing channels yields different results or profits for each marketing agency due to the marketing function activities, time, and costs involved. This can be seen in Table 7, as follows:

Table 7: Analysis of Margin and Income in Channel I

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/Kg)	Income (Rp/Kg)	Cost (Rp/Kg)	Margin (Rp/Kg)
1	Collector Trader	37.470	6.245	8.725	14.970
2	Sub-district Wholesaler	49.834	4.530	7.834	12.364
3	Regency/City Wholesalers	63.655	5.256	8.565	13.821
4	Retail Traders	73.150	6.650	2.845	9.495
	Amount		22.681	27.969	50.650

Table 7 above describes the revenue and marketing margins for each channel through which fresh seafood reaches the end consumer. The highest selling price in this channel is at the retailer level, at IDR 73,150/kg, while the highest margin is achieved by the middlemen. The differences in margins between each channel are due to the activities of marketing functions, costs, and the number of marketing institutions. As the middlemen, middlemen act as intermediaries between producers/fishermen and other intermediaries, these marketing institutions have numerous marketing functions, as shown in Table 1. The following is an analysis of margins and revenues for Channel II, as shown in Table 8:

Table 8: Margin and Revenue Analysis for Channel II

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/Kg)	Income (Rp/Kg)	Cost (Rp/Kg)	Margin (Rp/Kg)
1	Collector Trader	40.593	9.368	8.725	18.093
2	Retail Trader	54.582	9.084	4.825	13.909
	Amount		18.452	13.550	32.002

Table 8 above illustrates the differences in margins, costs, and revenue levels for each marketing agency in each channel, due to the different marketing functions. For example, a fish collector selling fish to a retailer incurs a cost of IDR 8,725/kg, resulting in a sales volume of IDR 40,593/kg. Meanwhile, the retailer sets a selling price of IDR 54,582/kg, but incurs a cost of IDR 4,825/kg, resulting in a cost difference of IDR 3,900/kg between the collector and retailer. Furthermore, the margin and revenue analysis for channel III is as follows:

Table 9: Margin and Revenue Analysis for Channel III

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/Kg)	Income (Rp/Kg)	Cost (Rp/Kg)	Margin (Rp/Kg)
1	Collector Trader	63.655	18.237	4.825	9.159
2	Sub-district Wholesaler	73.203	4.530	7.834	12.364
3	Retail Traders	78.752	10.272	4.825	15.097
	Amount		33.039	17.484	36.620

Table 9 above illustrates that the highest selling price is found at retailers because the goods/fish are received at the third level from the producer.

The various stages the goods go through to the end consumer, through collectors, wholesalers, and retailers, result in a price received by consumers of Rp 78,752, with costs of Rp 4,825/kg. Meanwhile, the lowest margin level is at the collector level, but the highest income level.

This occurs because the marketing function is treated more effectively than other marketing institutions. For channel IV, the margin and income levels are shown in the following table:

Table 10: Analysis of Margins and Income at the Retailer Level, Channel IV

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/Kg)	Income (Rp/Kg)	Cost (Rp/Kg)	Margin (Rp/Kg)
1	Manufacturer - Retailer - To End Consumer	49.214	8.202	7.262	15.404

Table 10 above illustrates that the selling price from retailers to end consumers is IDR 49,214/kg, and the price from producers to consumers is IDR 33,750/kg, meaning there is a price difference received by consumers of IDR 15,464/kg.

Meanwhile, the selling price for producers in channels I to III averages IDR 38,501/kg. This difference in prices received by producers through short channels is higher than through long channels, reflecting the theoretical/reference message that effective and efficient marketing of agricultural and sub-sector products is through short channels.

4. Marketing Channel Efficiency

Marketing efficiency is essentially the ratio of marketing output to input. Marketing output is the final sales proceeds received, while marketing input is the funds used to process and transport the product until it reaches the consumer.

The efficiency of fresh marine fish marketing channels from producers to consumers in the Pangkep area and other areas can be seen in Table 11 below:

Table 11. Efficiency and Profitability of Fresh Marine Fish Marketing Channels in Pangkep Regency

Table 11: Efficiency and Profitability of Fresh Sea Fish Marketing Channels in Pangkep Regency

No.	Channel	Efficiency (%)	Profit (Rp/Kg)
1	I	38,25	22.681
2	II	24,83	18.452
3	III	22,20	33.039
4	IV	14,75	8.202

Source: Primary data after processing

Table 11 above shows that the revenue from marketing fresh marine fish through channel III is IDR 33,039/kg, with an efficiency level of 22.20%. The lowest revenue was obtained through channel IV, at IDR 8,202.

An assessment of the marketing efficiency of fresh marine fish products was conducted to determine which channel is more efficient and yields higher profits.

Although theory suggests that shorter marketing channels are more efficient, this study found that efficient channels are those that generate higher profits.

CONCLUSION

This research, after conducting several studies, obtained several results using a matrix analysis of costs, margins, and revenues. The following preliminary conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) The costs, margins, and revenue levels of each marketing institution differ.
- 2) The revenue levels earned by marketing institutions vary.
- 3) The efficiency of marketing agricultural and fisheries products through short marketing channels.
- 4) The high marketing margins of each channel are influenced by the activities of marketing functions.
- 5) Marketing functions influence product quality levels and increase sales volume.

Bibliography

- 1) Anonim, 1999, Pengwilayahan Komoditi sebagai dasar pengembangan Wilayah Daerah Provinsi Sulawesi Selatan. -----, 2001, Manajemen Hasil Perikanan, Kantor Dinas Perikanan Kabupaten Pangkep. -----, 2001, Kabupaten Maros Dalam Angka Tahun 2010
- 2) Avonina, S. 2010. Pengembangan UKM sebagai Salah Satu Unit Usaha di Sektor Swasta. <http://ikm-sintang.com/2-industri-kecil-dan-menengah.html>. [16 Agustus 2010].
- 3) Beierlein, J.G. and M.W. Woolverton. 1991. *Agribusiness Marketing. The Management Perspective*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.
- 4) Clindiff W. Edwar, Still R. Richard and Govon A.P. Norman. 2010, *Fundamentals of Modern Marketing, Liberty*.
- 5) Davis, H.H and R.A. Goldberg. 2011. *A Concept of Agribusiness*. Buston: Graduate School of Business, Harvard University.
- 6) D.H. Swastha Basu. 1990. Saluran Pemasaran, Bagian Penerbitan Fak. Ekonomi Universitas Gajah Mada, Yogyakarta.
- 7) Downey D.W. and Erickson P. Steven, 2011, *Agribusiness Management*. Mc.Graw, Hill Book Company, New York.
- 8) Fleisher, B. 2012. *Agricultural Risk management*, Colorado dan London: Lynne Roenner Pub.
- 9) Gumbira-Said, E. Pengantar Manajemen Teknologi untuk Agribisnis” Makala Seminar, 1996, MMA-IPB, Bogor.
- 10) Endi. 2009. Artikel internet diakses di situs go-kerja.com/strategi-pemasaran/ pada tanggal 21 Mei 2010.
- 11) Guynor, G.H. 2009. *Acheving the Competitive Edge through Integrated Technology Management*, New York; McGraw Hill.
- 12) Iqbal dan Simandjuntak. 2004. Solusi Jitu bagi Pengusaha Kecil dan Menengah. Gramedia, Jakarta.
- 13) Imron, Dwi Agung Nugroho & Purwo Adi Wibowo. 2001. Analisis Pengaruh Orientasi Produk dan Orientasi Pasar Terhadap Kinerja Museum, Seminar Teknologi Informasi & Komunikasi Terapan.
- 14) Kotler, Neil G, Philip and Wendy. 2008. *Museum Marketing and Strategy: Designing missions*,
- 15) Kartasapoetra G. 1986, Marketing Produk Pertanian dan Industri, P.T. Bima Aksara, Jakarta.

- 16) Triyawan, A. (2021). *Influence Of Export And Import Toward Economic Growth In Canada In .*
- 17) Lokananta, A. C. (2021). *The Change of Reporter Communication Process at News Production in Pandemic. RSF Conference Series: Business, Management and Social Sciences*
- 18) Santika A, 1991. *Analisis Marjin Pemasaran Sayuran Dataran Tinggi di Provinsi Jawa Barat*, Fak.Pasca Sarjana IPB.
- 19) Tomek G. William and Robinson L. Kenneth, 2011. *Agricultural Product Proce*, Gernell University Press, Ithaca and London.